

GEOINFORMATION SYSTEMS IN THE ENERGY INDUSTRY

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Introduction

The article discusses the possibility and problems of using geographic information systems in the energy industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of legal regulation. As part of the study, the subject composition of legal relations in the field of GIS technology of industrial energy, integrated into a database of boron information, was examined. A legal analysis of the possibility of using geographic information systems at various stages of the life cycle of an energy installation, ranging from pre-design documentation to commissioning, was carried out. Information restricted for distribution has been determined. The legal security regime regarding information has been studied.

Key words: energy, geographic information system, topographic geodetic model, operating organization, energy sector, energy security, basic energy infrastructure base.

GEOINFORMATION SYSTEMS IN THE ENERGY INDUSTRY

Geographic information systems are a class of information systems that have their own characteristics. They are built taking into account the laws of geoinformatics and the methods used in this science. Geographic information systems as integrated information systems are designed to solve various problems of science and production based on the use of spatially localized data about objects. Geographic information system software, personnel and geographic data designed for the efficient entry, storage, updating, processing, analysis and visualization of data, all types of geographically organized information.

Geographic information systems are multifunctional tools for analyzing consolidated tabular, text and cartographic, demographic, and statistical data.

A geographic information system is a system capable of storing and using data about spatial and organizational objects. Geographic information systems are becoming increasingly common not only in traditional applications such as natural resource management, agriculture, ecology, cadastres, urban planning, but also in commercial structures - from energy and telecommunications to retail. As decision support systems, geographic information systems help to conduct analysis and provide noticeable advantages in their activities. Geographic information systems are an effective tool for selecting locations and identifying production facilities, dispatching and routing. Industry use of GIS technologies the capabilities of GIS technologies can be used in the electricity industry, design of engineering networks; – monitoring the condition of utility networks and preventing emergency situations, the electricity industry. To create a basis for the electricity industry, we must distribute the types of electricity industry. The use of geographic information systems (GIS) technology in the energy sector has a long successful history, great potential and rich prospects. The energy industry provides a favorable environment for large-scale use of the unique capabilities of geographic information systems. After all, most aspects of this multifaceted technological process have a significant spatial component and are tied to a specific territory or specific location. Geography-related data permeates all stages of the process: from field exploration, infrastructure creation and deployment, generation, transportation (transmission) and marketing. This fully applies to such areas of activity of energy companies as sales and dispatch (logistics), compliance with environmental requirements, security issues and emergency response, energy saving and increasing energy efficiency FEC. GIS, as a universal integration platform, can help improve the efficiency of the production process through the full management of almost all types of data. Complete and comprehensive data management (information support, modeling and analysis) based on GIS, especially when implemented at the

corporate level, eliminates unnecessary duplication of data sets and ensures continuity and consistency in the implementation of all phases of the project. Optimization of electrical grid operations must be integrated into GIS with real-time geo-survey and global positioning technology (GPS/GLONASS). To carry out operational geo-surveying, laptop computers or GIS receivers are used, which allows you to carry out measurements with accuracy verification directly at the work site. In addition to its use in operational processes, GIS technology is a powerful tool to support the management of all types of facilities and the overall spatially distributed infrastructure of companies in the energy industry. All information is stored in geodatabases and displayed in 2D, (or 3D) spatial representations and time dynamics. For example, in the world of assignment and purpose Electrical energy generation - Electricity generation is the process of converting various types of energy into electrical energy at industrial facilities called power plants. Currently, there are the following types of generation:

- Thermal power engineering. In this case, the thermal energy of combustion of organic fuels is converted into electrical energy. Thermal power engineering includes thermal power plants (TPPs), which come in two main types:

The Condensing power plants (KES, the old abbreviation GRES is also used);

- o District heating (thermal power plants, combined heat and power plants). Cogeneration is the combined production of electrical and thermal energy at the same station; CPP and CHP have similar technological processes. In both cases, there is a boiler in which fuel is burned and, due to the heat generated, steam under pressure is heated. Next, the heated steam is supplied to a steam turbine, where its thermal energy is converted into rotational energy. The turbine shaft rotates the rotor of the electric generator - thus the rotational energy is converted into electrical energy, which is supplied to the network. The fundamental difference between a CHP plant and a CPP is that part of the steam heated in the boiler is used for heat supply needs. The majority of power plants in the world (about 2/3 of all energy generated) are thermal power plants.

- Nuclear energy. This includes nuclear power plants (NPPs). In practice, nuclear power is often considered a subtype of thermal power, since, in general, the principle of generating electricity at nuclear power plants is the same as at thermal power plants. Only in this case, thermal energy is released not during the combustion of fuel, but during the fission of atomic nuclei in a nuclear reactor. Further, the electricity production scheme is no fundamentally different from a thermal power plant: steam is heated in a reactor, enters a steam turbine, etc. Due to some design features of nuclear power plants, it is unprofitable to use them in combined generation, although separate experiments have been carried out in this direction;

Hydropower. This includes hydroelectric power plants (HPP). In hydropower, the kinetic energy of water flow is converted into electrical energy. To do this, with the help of dams on rivers, a difference in water surface levels is artificially created (the so-called upper and lower pools). Under the influence of gravity, water flows from the upper pool to the lower one through special channels in which water turbines are located, the blades of which are spun by the water flow. The turbine rotates the rotor of the electric generator. A special type of hydroelectric power station is pumped storage power station (PSPP). They cannot be considered generating facilities in their pure form, since they consume almost as much electricity as they produce, but such stations are very effective in unloading the network during peak hours. Recently, studies have shown that the power of sea currents is many orders of magnitude greater than the power of all rivers in the world. In this regard, the creation of experimental offshore hydroelectric power plants is underway.

• Wind energy - the use of kinetic wind energy to generate electricity;

Solar energy - obtaining electrical energy from the energy of solar rays;

Common disadvantages of wind and solar energy are the relative low power of generators and their high cost. Also, in both cases, storage capacity is required for nighttime (for solar energy) and calm (for wind energy) periods;

The Geothermal energy is the use of the Earth's natural heat to generate electrical energy. In essence, geothermal stations are ordinary thermal power plants, in which the heat source for heating steam is not a boiler or a nuclear reactor, but underground sources of natural heat. The disadvantage of such stations is the geographical limitation of their use: geothermal stations are cost-effective to build only in regions of tectonic activity, that is, where natural heat sources are most accessible;

The Hydrogen energy - the use of hydrogen as an energy fuel has great prospects: hydrogen has a very high combustion efficiency, its resource is practically unlimited, the combustion of hydrogen is absolutely environmentally friendly (the product of combustion in an oxygen atmosphere is distilled water). However, hydrogen energy is currently not able to fully satisfy the needs of mankind due to the high cost of producing pure hydrogen and the technical problems of transporting it in large quantities. In fact, hydrogen is just a carrier of energy, and does not in any way solve the problem of extracting this energy.

The Tidal energy uses the energy of sea tides. The spread of this type of electric power generation is hampered by the need for the coincidence of too many factors when designing a power plant: What is needed is not just a sea coast, but a coast where the tides are strong enough and constant. For example, the Black Sea coast is not suitable for the construction of tidal power plants, since water level differences in the Black Sea at high and low tide are minimal.

The Wave energy, upon careful consideration, may turn out to be the most promising. Waves are concentrated energy from the same solar radiation and wind.

The wave power in different places can exceed 100 kW per linear meter of wave front. There is almost always excitement, even in calm conditions (“dead swell”). In the Black Sea, the average wave power is approximately 15 kW/m. Northern seas of Russia - up to 100 kW/m. Harnessing waves can provide energy to marine and coastal communities. Waves can propel ships, the average pitching

power of a ship is several times greater than the power of its propulsion system. But so far wave power plants have not gone beyond single prototypes.

By using isoelectric energy in Uzbekistan, indicated in the above direction, we can close the full consumption of power and can also export from neighboring countries. If we clarify the scale of our Uzbekistan 448,978 km², we will see that the place for various energy inventions in our country has a very pleasant and convenient potential for achieving progress in energy technology, If we study what is happening in neighboring countries on energy, we will see that every year the demand for energy increases, but also the alternative to the invention of energy increases.

classic means.

Renewable Energy

These are the facts on the dynamics, we must be ahead of the curve and must take into account every potential for growth and development and take advantage of every chance for energy.

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